

CORDEX-CMIP6 Data Request: CORE Aerosol variables

ag - aggregation for the highest-frequency output; i: instantaneous; a: averaged over output interval (in model); c: cumulative over sampling period

Version: 22 sept 2022

output variable name	units	ag	long_name	standard_name	Output frequency					Priority	Comments
					mon	day	6hr	3hr	1hr		
abs550aer	1	i	Ambient Aerosol Absorption Optical Thickness at 550 nm	atmosphere_absorption_optical_thickness_due_to_ambient_aerosol_particles	x	x			x	CORE	1hr optional (considered for Tier1)
asy550aer	1	i	Aerosol Asymmetry Parameter at 550 nm	asymmetry_factor_of_ambient_aerosol_particles	x	x			x	CORE	1hr optional (considered for Tier1)
od550aer	1	i	Ambient Aerosol Optical Thickness at 550nm	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_ambient_aerosol_particles	x	x			x	CORE	1hr optional (considered for Tier1)
od550bc	1	i	Black Carbon Aerosol Optical Thickness at 550nm	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_black_carbon_ambient_aerosol_particles	x	x			x	CORE	1hr optional (considered for Tier1)
od550dust	1	i	Dust Aerosol Optical Thickness at 550nm	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_dust_ambient_aerosol_particles	x	x			x	CORE	1hr optional (considered for Tier1)
od550nh4	1	i	Ammonium Aerosol Optical Thickness at 550nm	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_ammonium_ambient_aerosol_particles	x	x			x	CORE	1hr optional (considered for Tier1)
od550no3	1	i	Nitrate Aerosol Optical Thickness at 550nm	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_nitrate_ambient_aerosol_particles	x	x			x	CORE	1hr optional (considered for Tier1)
od550oa	1	i	Organic Matter Aerosol Optical Thickness at 550nm	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_organic_matter_ambient_aerosol_particles	x	x			x	CORE	1hr optional (considered for Tier1)
od550o4	1	i	Sulfate Aerosol Optical Thickness at 550nm	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_sulfate_ambient_aerosol_particles	x	x			x	CORE	1hr optional (considered for Tier1)
od550ss	1	i	Sea-Salt Aerosol Optical Thickness at 550nm	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_sea-salt_ambient_aerosol_particles	x	x			x	CORE	1hr optional (considered for Tier1)
ssa550aer	1	i	Aerosol Single Scattering Albedo at 550 nm	single_scattering_albedo_in_air_due_to_ambient_aerosol_particles	x	x			x	CORE	1hr optional (considered for Tier1)
toz	DU	i	Total Column Ozone	equivalent_thickness_at_stp_of_atmosphere_ozone_content	x	x				CORE	

CORDEX-CMIP6 Data Request: Tier 2 Aerosol variables

ag - agregation for the highest-frequency output: i: instantaneous; a: averaged over output interval (in model); c: cumulative over sampling period

Version: 22 sept 2022

output variable name	units	ag	long_name	standard_name	Output frequency					Priority	Comments
					mon	day	6hr	3hr	1hr		
abs1000bc	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs1000dust	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs1000nh4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs1000no3	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs1000oa	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs1000so4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs1000ss	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs350bc	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs350dust	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs350nh4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs350no3	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs350oa	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs350so4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs350ss	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs440bc	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs440dust	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs440nh4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs440no3	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs440oa	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs440so4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs440ss	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs550bc	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs550dust	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs550nh4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs550no3	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs550oa	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs550so4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs550ss	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs870bc	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs870dust	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs870nh4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs870no3	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs870oa	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs870so4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
abs870ss	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od1000bc	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od1000dust	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od1000nh4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od1000no3	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od1000oa	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od1000so4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od1000ss	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od350bc	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od350dust	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od350nh4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od350no3	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od350oa	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od350so4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od350ss	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od440bc	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od440dust	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od440nh4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od440no3	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od440oa	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od440so4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od440ss	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od870bc	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od870dust	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od870nh4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od870no3	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od870oa	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od870so4	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
od870ss	1	i			x	x				TIER 2	
chepnh4	kg m-2 s-1	c			x	x				TIER 2	List of levels: 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 650, 700, 750, 800, 850, 900, 925, 950, 975, 1000 hPa (all in 1 file if possible)
chepno3	kg m-2 s-1	c			x	x				TIER 2	List of levels: 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 650, 700, 750, 800, 850, 900, 925, 950, 975, 1000 hPa (all in 1 file if possible)
cheapso4	kg m-2 s-1	c			x	x				TIER 2	List of levels: 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 650, 700, 750, 800, 850, 900, 925, 950, 975, 1000 hPa (all in 1 file if possible)
chepso4	kg m-2 s-1	c			x	x				TIER 2	List of levels: 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 650, 700, 750, 800, 850, 900, 925, 950, 975, 1000 hPa (all in 1 file if possible)
chepsoa	kg m-2 s-1	c			x	x				TIER 2	List of levels: 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 650, 700, 750, 800, 850, 900, 925, 950, 975, 1000 hPa (all in 1 file if possible)
concbc	kg m-3	i			x	x				TIER 2	List of levels: 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 650, 700, 750, 800, 850, 900, 925, 950, 975, 1000 hPa (all in 1 file if possible)
concdust	kg m-3	i			x	x				TIER 2	List of levels: 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 650, 700, 750, 800, 850, 900, 925, 950, 975, 1000 hPa (all in 1 file if possible)
concnh4	kg m-3	i			x	x				TIER 2	List of levels: 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 650, 700, 750, 800, 850, 900, 925, 950, 975, 1000 hPa (all in 1 file if possible)
concnno3	kg m-3	i			x	x				TIER 2	List of levels: 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 650, 700, 750, 800, 850, 900, 925, 950, 975, 1000 hPa (all in 1 file if possible)
concoa	kg m-3	i			x	x				TIER 2	List of levels: 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 650, 700, 750, 800, 850, 900, 925, 950, 975, 1000 hPa (all in 1 file if possible)
conco4	kg m-3	i			x	x				TIER 2	List of levels: 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 650, 700, 750, 800, 850, 900, 925, 950, 975, 1000 hPa (all in 1 file if possible)
concss	kg m-3	i			x	x				TIER 2	List of levels: 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 650, 700, 750, 800, 850, 900, 925, 950, 975, 1000 hPa (all in 1 file if possible)